

Azolla biomass production, Jorhat, India, 1981-82.

Treatments ^a	Azolla biomass (t/ha)												Mean
	1981						1982						
	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	
L ₀ P ₀ I ₁	23.8	6.8	21.0	19.3	14.0	18.5	6.3	18.4	17.5	19.4	21.2	26.5	17.7
L ₀ P ₀ I ₂	28.5	6.7	26.0	22.2	17.4	20.0	8.8	15.0	17.0	18.4	24.0	26.4	19.2
L ₀ P ₁ I ₁	30.3	14.2	27.5	20.8	17.5	25.3	13.5	21.9	25.3	20.2	26.0	29.6	22.7
L ₀ P ₂ I ₁	34.6	14.0	31.0	26.1	23.7	21.3	11.0	21.0	26.4	24.7	22.2	30.3	23.8
L ₀ P ₁ I ₂	29.5	14.7	30.0	25.5	26.6	26.9	15.7	22.5	25.1	20.9	27.1	32.4	24.7
L ₀ P ₂ I ₂	31.9	13.7	32.4	27.7	25.3	30.4	16.3	17.0	19.5	25.0	24.6	34.9	24.9
L ₁ P ₀ I ₁	16.0	4.1	26.0	17.3	12.9	15.4	11.3	12.9	18.6	20.5	23.7	30.8	17.4
L ₁ P ₀ I ₂	28.3	5.6	25.8	20.9	18.0	26.5	18.5	17.0	20.3	19.3	24.4	18.6	20.3
L ₁ P ₁ I ₁	30.0	16.9	31.2	35.2	24.7	28.4	19.2	21.9	20.8	28.1	27.9	35.1	26.6
L ₁ P ₁ I ₂	35.3	12.5	30.4	32.0	27.6	29.2	17.4	25.1	27.2	25.4	29.2	39.3	27.7
L ₁ P ₂ I ₁	31.3	15.9	28.8	30.1	30.1	26.0	19.6	23.0	22.9	24.8	29.9	28.4	25.9
L ₁ P ₂ I ₂	33.7	16.0	33.8	31.0	26.4	30.1	18.4	26.3	26.1	20.5	30.0	34.1	27.2
Mean	29.4	11.7	28.7	25.7	22.0	24.8	14.7	20.2	22.2	22.4	25.8	30.6	
	<i>Mean av water temp (°C)</i>												
	29	38	32	31	26	24	22	25	28	30	30	30	

Season (mo) CD (0.05) 2.768
 Lime (L) 1.151
 Phosphate (P) 1.384
 CV = 14.77%

^a L₀ = no lime, L₁ = 1 t lime/ha, P₀ = no P, P₁ = 9 kg P/ha, P₂ = 18 kg P/ha, I₁ = 0.5 t inoculum/ha, I₂ = 1 t inoculum/ha.

Jul, and was lowest in Aug. Production increased in Sep and then remained stable until Dec (see table). Variations in production were related to weather, particularly temperature. In Aug, when production was lowest, water temperature reached 44° C and averaged 38° C.

Production also varied with nutrient management. Applying 1 t lime and 18 kg P/ha significantly increased production over no-lime and no-P treatments (see table). P affected production more than lime did. Inoculum amount did not affect biomass production. *ℒ*

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Effect of salinity on *Azolla pinnata*

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We studied the effect of salinity on *A. pinnata*, Coimbatore strain, with a soil extract solution with 20 ppm superphosphate as base medium. Sodium chloride was applied at 0.01,

0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06, 0.07, 0.08, 0.09, 0.1, and 0.2%. *A. pinnata* was inoculated at 5 g per plastic container and fresh weight was recorded after 14 d. In another experiment, 500 ppm neem *Azadirachta indica* cake was added to the medium.

A. pinnata yield decreased as salinity increased (see table), but neem cake reduced the detrimental effect of salinity. *ℒ*

Effect of salinity on *A. pinnata*, Tamil Nadu, India.

Sodium chloride (%)	Biomass (g/tub)	% decrease over control	Biomass (g/tub) with neem cake amendment (500 ppm)	% increase or decrease over control
Control without superphosphate	5.3	-	5.4	-
Neem cake alone	NT ^a	-	8.8	+62
0.01	5.2	3	8.5	+57
0.02	5.0	6	7.5	+38
0.03	4.7	11	7.0	+30
0.04	4.7	11	6.7	+24
0.05	4.6	13	5.4	+ 0
0.06	4.4	18	5.2	- 3
0.07	4.3	20	5.2	- 3
0.08	4.0	25	5.2	- 3
0.09	4.0	25	4.8	-11
0.10	3.7	31	4.7	-13
0.20	3.6	32	4.0	-26
SE	0.006		0.577	
CD	0.017		1.678	

^aNot tested.

Rice response to and residual effect of Zn application in a sandy lowland soil

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In 1981 wet season and 1981-82 dry season, we studied IR880 rice response to and residual effect of Zn application in a sandy soil with 1.77 ppm available Zn and pH 7.1. Zn at 0, 2.8, 5.8, 8.5, and 11.5 kg/ha was applied before seeding.

In wet season, plots were in a randomized complete block design with eight replications. To study residual effect in dry season, Zn was applied to four of the same plots and the remaining four received no Zn.

In wet season, all treatments were significantly better than no-Zn control. Rice yield increased from 3.4 to 4.5 t/ha (see figure). In dry season, rice yield increased from 3.5 to 5.0 t/ha (see figure), and best results were obtained with 8.5 and 11.5 kg Zn/ha.

Zn application had a substantial residual effect (see table). Although

Response of IR880 to Zn application in sandy soil, Sancti-Spiritus, Cuba.

initial soil Zn was a little more than the critical levels of 1.0 and 1.5 ppm, the positive response to Zn application may have been due to the near neutral pH of the soil. *S*

Residual effect of Zn in a sandy lowland rice soil, Sancti-Spiritus, Cuba.

Treatment (kg Zn/ha)	Zn (ppm)			
	1981		Jul	1982 ^c
	Jun ^a	Dec ^b	with Zn	no Zn
Control	1.77	1.97	1.97	1.97
2.9	1.72	3.79	3.00	3.83
5.8	1.93	4.47	3.59	2.75
8.5	1.89	4.94	4.59	2.89
11.5	1.93	4.41	4.58	4.11

^a Before seeding. ^b After first crop. ^c After second crop.

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Potential of rice-based multiple cropping systems in Pakistan

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In 1984, we surveyed 240 rice farmers to determine the economic potential of mungbean and sunflower in the thesils

Table 1. Comparison of base model with 1983-84 crop plan on the Daska farm.

	Actual cropping pattern	Optimal cropping pattern, base model
Value of objective function		\$105 6
	<i>Area (acres)</i>	
Basmati rice	4	5.7 ^a
IRRI rice	2	1.3 ^b
Kharif fodder	2.1	3
Wheat	11	10.2 ^c
Rabi fodder	1.5	2.7
	<i>Cropping intensity (%)</i>	
	175	178

^a Basmati on excellent land with farmyard manure (FYM) (2.62 acres) + Basmati on average land with FYM (3.1 acres) = 5.72. ^b IRRI rice grown on excellent land with FYM. ^c Wheat on excellent land (3.9 acres) + on average land (6.3 acres) = 10.2.

Table 2. Comparison of base model with sunflower and sunflower and mungbean for the Daska farm.

Activity	Optimal cropping pattern		
	Base model	Sunflower	Sunflower and mungbean
	<i>Value of objective function (\$)</i>		
	984	2017	2990
	<i>Area (acres)</i>		
Basmati on excellent land with farmyard manure (FYM)	2.6	3.9	3.9
Basmati on good land with FYM	3.1	1.26	1.26
IRRI rice on excellent land with FYM	1.3	-	-
Wheat on excellent land	3.9	3.9	3.9
Wheat on average land	6.3	-	3.9
Kharif fodder	3.0	2.1	2.1
Rabi fodder	2.7	1.5	2.1
Spring sunflower	-	7.5	4.9
Kharif sunflower	-	5.6	5.6
Mungbean	-	-	8.0
	<i>Cropping intensity (%)</i>		
	178	200	261

of Daska, Sheikhpura, and Hafizabad in the Punjab. Short-duration (55 to 60 d) mungbean varieties developed at the Nuclear Institute of Agriculture and Biology, Faisalabad, can be sown in Apr, after wheat harvest, and harvested before basmati rice is planted in Jun. Sunflower can be sown in Feb instead of late, low yielding wheat or in July as an

alternative to rice.

Mathematical models were constructed of representative farms in Daska and Hafizabad. Sheikhpura conditions are very similar to those in Hafizabad.

Table 1 compares Daska farmers' cropping patterns for 1983-84 with profit maximizing solutions. The model